

Preparation of 2.5DSiO_{2f}/SiN Composites and Interface Analysis

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Abstract: The 2.5DSiO_{2f}/SiN composites were prepared by precursor impregnation and pyrolysis using 2.5D quartz fiber reinforced as a precursor and use perhydro polysilazane as ceramic precursor. Experimental results indicated that after 5 rounds of impregnation-curing-pyrolysis process, composite material density is 1.70g/cm³, the dielectric constant and dielectric loss tangent values are 3.25, 0.012, respectively, the formation of a strong fiber interface, flexural strength of composites is only 29.74MPa. With BN coating on quartz fiber, improve the fiber matrix interface, preventing the fiber and precursor pyrolysis at high temperature interface reaction, after 5 rounds of impregnation- curing- pyrolysis process, 2.5DSiO_{2f}/SiBN composites flexural strength reach to 110.4MPa, the dielectric constant and the loss tangent are 3.16 and 0.009.

Fig.1 Structure of perhydro polysilazane(PHPS)

Fig.2 Flow chart for preparing 2.5D SiO_{2f}/SiN composite by PIP process

Fig.3 Elements of PHPS pyrolysis productions

Tab.1 Contents of PHPS pyrolysis productions

Element	Si	N	O
Mass percent	56.70	28.68	14.61
Atomic percent	40.54	41.12	18.34

Fig.4 Photographs of 2.5D SiO₂f/SiN composite

Table 2 Properties of 2.5D SiO₂f/SiN composites

PIP cycle (time)	Density g/cm ³	Bending strength MPa	Dielectric constant (10GHz)	tan δ (10GHz)
1	1.42	18.24	2.96	0.008
2	1.58	21.89	3.03	0.010
3	1.68	26.03	3.12	0.010
4	1.71	29.74	3.25	0.012

Fig.5 Displacement load curve of 2.5D SiO₂f/SiN composite

Fig.6 SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of 2.5D SiO₂/SiN composites

Fig.7 SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of composites

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